

Uncertainty Assessment for the Imputation of an Area Survey

Sean Rhodes¹, Arthur Rosales¹, Luca Sartore^{1,2}, Tara Murphy¹

¹National Agricultural Statistics Service, USDA, 1400 Independence Avenue,
Washington, DC 20250

²National Institute of Statistical Sciences, 1750 K Street NW Suite 1100,
Washington, DC 20006

Abstract

Every year the United States (US) Department of Agriculture’s National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) conducts the June Area Survey (JAS) based on an area frame, which has complete coverage of all land in the contiguous US. The data collected from the JAS are used to supply direct estimates of acreage and measures of sampling coverage for NASS’s list frame, which consists of all known farms in the US. Response rates have been declining in many federal surveys, including the JAS, leading to increased item and unit nonresponse. NASS has begun exploration of utilizing automatic imputation for the JAS using various machine learning models. Previous research has found that NASS’s Predictive Cropland Data Layer (PCDL) and Crop Sequence Boundaries (CSBs) have good predictive power for corn and soybeans (two major US crop commodities). This paper explores the relationship between the PCDL entropy levels and the estimated planted acres based on the CSBs and PCDL values, administrative data and survey data to estimate the uncertainty associated with the JAS imputed acreage.

Key Words: administrative data, geospatial data, nonresponse, inflated beta distribution, semiparametric generalized regression, survey data

1. Introduction

The National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) is the statistical arm of the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA). NASS is responsible for conducting over 100 different surveys and 400 national reports annually, as well as the Census of Agriculture every five years. The June Area Survey (JAS) is NASS’s largest annual survey, which is based on an area frame that covers all land in the US (except for Alaska). This survey collects data that are used to supply direct estimates of crop acreage, livestock inventories, and measures of sampling coverage of the NASS list frame. The area frame is composed of primary sampling units (PSUs), which are stretches of land delineated by permanent boundaries, such as roads, rivers, etc. PSUs are stratified by land-use occurring within their bounds, focusing on the intensity of cultivated crops. The JAS has a multi-stage design, where secondary sampling units called “segments” are selected from the PSUs for enumeration. These segments are approximately one square mile in size and may contain multiple “tracts” of land. Each tract represents a unique farm operation. Approximately 9,000 segments are sampled each year. All or only a portion of a farm may lie within a segment, depending on the number of fields within a farming operation and the location of those fields.

The JAS has complex challenges of nonresponse compared to other NASS surveys. The JAS data collection has traditionally been based entirely on in-person interviews, which is expensive. Data collection occurs across the contiguous US during a two-week period early in June. These aspects restrict the time and money that can feasibly be spent on contact attempts and refusal conversions. Item and unit nonresponse are imputed so that all records are complete. Currently, statisticians in

the NASS regional field offices manually impute these records using several sources of information. Staff use the June Area Land tool, which links the JAS-tract information and auxiliary data, to access this information.

Part of the data currently used for studying the JAS automatic imputation originate from the Farm Service Agency (FSA) Form-578. Farmers participating in USDA programs or purchasing crop insurance must report their crop plantings each year via Form-578. Since FSA conducts multiple checks to this program data, the data are considered of high quality and are regarded in this paper as ground truth. Historical FSA data are available for JAS imputation. However, current-year FSA data are not available until mid-July so they cannot be used for imputation or in the estimation process. They can be used to assess the accuracy of imputation procedures at the end of the season.

Historical Cropland Data Layers (CDLs; Boryan et al., 2011) are available and can be used for JAS imputation. This is a crop-specific landcover-classification dataset that NASS has published yearly for the conterminous US since 2008. The CDL is based on in-season FSA data and remote sensing data. It has been used to identify field boundaries, planting history, crop rotation cycles, and field-level acreage by crop type (Abernethy et al., 2023). Although the end-of-year classification provided by the CDL is quite accurate at the state level, CDL production does not begin until mid-July when the FSA data become available.

The Predictive Copland Data Layer (PCDL) provides information for imputation. NASS developed the PCDL as a basis for pre-season crop-type predictions with related uncertainty measures based on crop rotation patterns using historical CDLs corrected with FSA data (Sartore et al. 2022) and higher-order Markov chains (Sartore et al. 2023). The PCDL offers a probabilistic land-cover prediction. The uncertainty measures based on entropy (Shannon, 1948) can be used to assess the accuracy of the crop classification provided by PCDL.

The entropy layer of the PCDL is designed to quantify the confidence of the predictions for areas of interest. Areas of low entropy are usually fields with simple historical patterns, where the next crop rotation is easier to predict. Areas of high entropy are often fields characterized by complex patterns where crops change without any apparent logic. The entropy, however, is not a direct measure of the acreage uncertainty. In fact, Sartore et al. (2022) further investigated the relationship between segment-level entropy and acreage error for corn and soybeans.

Crop Sequence Boundaries (CSBs; Hunt et al., 2023) is a geospatial layer of the boundaries associated with agricultural fields in the contiguous US. Abernethy et al. (2023) extensively discussed the use of machine learning algorithms for the pre-season forecast of crop-specific planted acreage at the field level using CSBs. Random forests (Breiman, 2001; Johnson and Mueller, 2021), extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost; Chen and Guestrin, 2016), and artificial neural networks (Zhang et al., 2019) were compared. In general, XGBoost performed the best when using six-year rotations, spatial coordinates of CSB-centroids, categorical identifiers of agricultural statistical districts, and the size of CSBs (in acres). However, the predictions obtained with XGBoost did not have associated measures of uncertainty.

As with all imputation, manual imputation results in increased error. The manual imputation is time consuming and results in more variability due to differences in staff members' decisions, which is difficult to measure. Murphy et al. (2022) developed an automatic imputation approach for the JAS, which would eliminate the variability due to differences in staff members' imputation decisions. Because the final automatic imputation approach is likely to depend on multiple sources, it is important to not only quantify the uncertainty associated with each information source but also the that associated from the use of multiple sources.

In this paper, the automatically imputed values for planted acreage of corn and soybeans are obtained by fusing the tract-level information from the PCDL and CSBs. Then an approach for computing the tract-level variance associated with the imputed acreage is proposed. A semi-parametric model is used to assess whether the entropy layer of the PCDL can be used to determine

the variability of imputation error. At the same time, the approach allows one to control for the size of the tracts. This new perspective is designed to fully incorporate all sources of variation within the standard errors (SEs) of the final state-level estimates.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the semi-parametric model and the methodology to compute the SEs due to tract-level imputation. Section 3 presents an application based on JAS 2021 data from eight Corn Belt States (i.e., Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, Ohio, and Wisconsin). Final remarks are provided in Section 4.

2. Methodology

The arithmetic average of the tract-level acreage computed using several data sources is considered here, which is different from the model-based approach of Murphy et al. (2022). The tract-level acreage predictions resulting from the PCDL, the CSBs, and the digitized JAS sampled segments were tabulated. Each JAS segment is geospatially linked to the PCDL and CSBs. Each tract (land associated with a single operation) within a segment is identified by a unique letter (see Figure 1).

Each CSB is a geospatial layer of polygons stored in a vector data format. Once the crop predictions are calculated using XGBoost for each polygon, the data are rasterized to form a 30m x 30m grid. This resolution was chosen for compatibility with other NASS raster datasets. The rasterization process resulted in the removal of polygons that cover areas smaller than 900m². As a result, the crop-type predicted for the CSBs is assigned to the corresponding pixels. The rasterized CSB-prediction data are then tabulated by counting the pixels of each crop-type within the digitized-tract boundaries. The pixels that straddle a tract boundary are considered for tabulation only if the majority of their area is contained in the tract. The summary acreage from the modeled CSBs is denoted by $\hat{A}_{i,C}$, for every JAS tract i . The resulting data frame with the CSB predictions is organized to have the digitized tracts by row and the acreage of each landcover type by column (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: An illustration of the tabulation of CSB data within JAS digitized tracts. The different colored swaths of area represent a pixel in the CSB data, shaded by a landcover type (yellow for corn and green for soybeans). The red boundary lines represent digitized tracts. The table demonstrates the result of the tabulation.

The PCDL is based on a 30m x 30m grid and stored in a raster format. Predicted tract acreages are tabulated and tabulated with the same process used for the CSBs. The acreage produced by the PCDL summaries is denoted by $\hat{A}_{i,P}$, for every JAS tract i . In contrast, the entropy layer of the PCDL is summarized using the median of pixels contained in a digitized tract (denoted by \hat{H}_i , for every JAS tract i).

The tracts within each JAS sample segment have been hand digitized since 2021. These are placed in a GIS layer, and the size of each tract is determined. The digitized JAS tracts within a sampled segment are linked to survey, PCDL, CSB, and FSA-578 data by performing a spatial join between the digitized tract boundaries and FSA Common Land Units (CLUs; USDA FSA, 2022). The spatial join is performed under the condition that the FSA CLU centroid must be contained within a JAS

digitized tract to be considered a match to that tract. By this process, the reported Form-578 data could be spatially linked to a digitized tract via the CLUs. Some FSA data were lost due to mismatches between IDs in the Form-578 reports and the CLU files. Additionally, it is technically possible that the spatial join method results in a loss of FSA data. For example, if a field overlaps a JAS digitized tract but the centroid is outside of the tract, it is excluded from the join. However, agreement between crop fields delineated by digitized tracts and FSA CLUs was high because similar rules were observed for their creation (i.e., by avoiding cutting across homogenous fields).

Once the three summary datasets (for the PCDL, CSBs, and FSA) are linked together, the arithmetic average between PCDL and CSB summaries is applied and is studied here for the development of an SE estimator. However, the tabulated acreage predictions from both the PCDL and CSBs were provided without measures of uncertainty. The correlation between these two sets of predictions is not quantified. Therefore, a new sophisticated technique for estimating the SE associated with the average of the prediction summaries is needed.

The Generalized Additive Models for Location, Scale and Shape (GAMLSS; Rigby and Stasinopoulos, 2005) is used to explore the variability of the imputation errors. The GAMLSS provides a semi-parametric framework for modelling the first four conditional moments of the response variable for a given set of covariates. This generalized approach originally made use of basis functions (such as B-splines, P-splines, etc.) to better represent nonlinear effects, which are denoted by $s(\cdot)$.

To estimate the SEs for the imputed values. Let A_i be the ground-truth FSA acreage of a specific commodity planted within the digitized tract i . Let W_i be the total size of the JAS digitized tract i expressed in acres. Let \hat{A}_i be the arithmetic average between the PCDL and CSB predicted acreage computed for the digitized tract i ; that is,

$$\hat{A}_i = \frac{\hat{A}_{i,P} + \hat{A}_{i,C}}{2}.$$

The absolute value of the relative error made when imputing the acreage of the tract i is defined as

$$Y_i = \left| \frac{\hat{A}_i - A_i}{W_i} \right|,$$

where Y_i is assumed to be distributed as an inflated beta random variable, which also accounts for zeros and ones (Ospina and Ferrari, 2010). The inflated beta distribution is defined as a mixture of three components. The first two components are designed to model the discrete outcomes with probability p_0 and p_1 for the zeros and the ones, respectively. The third component is formulated for the continuous outcomes in the open interval (0,1) such that their probability of occurrence is $1 - p_0 - p_1$. Furthermore, the continuous outcomes are assumed to be generated from a beta distribution with mean $\mu \in (0,1)$ and variance $\mu(1 - \mu)/\sigma$, where $\sigma \in (0,1)$, such that the density function is

$$f_B(y; \mu, \sigma) = \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{\sigma}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\mu}{\sigma}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{1-\mu}{\sigma}\right)} y^{\mu/\sigma-1} (1-y)^{(1-\mu)/\sigma-1}.$$

According to the parametrization provided by Rigby et al. (2019), the parameters $\nu \in \mathbb{R}_+$ and $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_+$ are used to control the probabilities of the mixture, such that $p_0 = \nu/(1 + \tau + \nu)$, and $p_1 = \tau/(1 + \tau + \nu)$. Therefore, the density function of the inflated Beta distribution is defined as

$$f_Y(y; \mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau) = (1 + \tau + \nu)^{-1} \begin{cases} \nu, & \text{if } y = 0, \\ f_B(y; \mu, \sigma), & \text{if } y \in (0,1), \\ \tau, & \text{if } y = 1, \end{cases}$$

where the parameters μ , σ , ν and τ may assume functional forms that make the parameters dependent on covariates.

Generalized regression is achieved using the logit-link function, for μ and σ , and the log-link function, for ν and τ . The P-Splines are added to the linear terms for controlling the parameter values of the inflated beta distribution. Once the estimation is performed via the penalized maximum likelihood, the expectation

$$E[Y_i|X_i] = \frac{\tau + \mu}{1 + \tau + \nu}$$

and the variance

$$\text{Var}[Y_i|X_i] = \frac{\tau^2}{(1 + \tau + \nu)(\tau + \nu)} + \frac{\mu(1 - \mu)\sigma}{1 + \tau + \nu} + \frac{\tau + \nu}{(1 + \tau + \nu)^2} \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau + \nu} - \mu \right)^2$$

are computed for given covariates X_i (which govern the effects associated with the parameters of the inflated beta distribution). Under unbiasedness assumptions (i.e., $E[\hat{A}_i - A_i|X_i] = 0$), the following equalities hold:

$$E[Y_i^2|X_i] = E \left[\left(\frac{\hat{A}_i - A_i}{W_i} \right)^2 \middle| X_i \right] = \frac{\text{Var}[\hat{A}_i|X_i]}{W_i^2}.$$

Hence, the SE associated with the imputed value \hat{A}_i is computed as

$$\text{SE}[\hat{A}_i|X_i] = \sqrt{\text{Var}[\hat{A}_i|X_i]} = W_i \sqrt{E[Y_i^2|X_i]} = W_i \sqrt{\text{Var}[Y_i|X_i] + E[Y_i|X_i]^2}. \quad (1)$$

This regression procedure assumes the availability of FSA data, which are not available for the JAS. Thus, the direct quantification of the imputation error is not possible. However, previous year data can be used to fit a model for predicting current-year SEs assuming that the parameter estimates are similar for consecutive years. If this assumption is satisfied, reliable SEs can be provided by the GAMLSS proposed above. Moreover, the SEs produced around mid-June can be successively compared with end-of-year results (produced when all data are available). This comparison is used for evaluating if the model needs to be improved by addressing potential issues caused by unforeseen temporal dynamics. In fact, under- and over-dispersion could be associated with the changing accuracy of the PCDL and CSB predictions.

3. Application

Exploring the uncertainty associated with the 2021 imputed acreage of a JAS tract is the primary objective of this application. The JAS data are collected on various crops; however, only planted acreage for corn is studied here. The predicted acres are compared to the FSA administrative data to assess the reliability, accuracy, and precision of the imputation process, and the associated SEs of the predictions are evaluated.

The geographical setting of this study is restricted to the Corn Belt, which includes the following states: Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, Ohio, and Wisconsin. The maximum area of the tracts was limited to 160 acres, which correspond to the size of a large field in the US Midwest. This upper bound was adopted to remove 170 JAS tracts, which were identified as influential tracts and extreme outliers. Once data cleaning was completed, the remaining 5,708 JAS tracts were analyzed.

When conducting the exploratory analysis, the absolute relative error was found to be positively skewed. Several imputation errors were very small, and a considerable number were found to be exactly zero (see Figure 2). Nonetheless, a few records were closer to one, and an even smaller number (although not negligible) were exactly one. For these reasons, the inflated beta was regarded as a candidate distribution to study nonlinear relationships among imputation errors and covariates.

Figure 2: The scatterplot between entropy and absolute relative error is shown on the left. The histogram of the absolute relative error is shown on the right.

The variability of the JAS tract-level imputation errors were studied using the GAMLSS (see Section 2). The absolute relative error was used as the response variable of two regression models. The first model used the median entropy from the PCDL as a covariate. The second model included the median PCDL entropy and the effects due to prediction disagreements, which were measured as the squared relative difference between the PCDL and CSB predictions; that is,

$$\hat{D}_i = \left(\frac{\hat{A}_{i,P} - \hat{A}_{i,C}}{W_i} \right)^2,$$

for every digitized tract i . Note that smaller values of \hat{D}_i are more likely associated with absence of errors but, as the squared relative difference increases, the imputation error and its variability also increase. Therefore, the acreage uncertainty was first studied across entropy levels, and successively, by combining entropy and prediction differences.

The first model was developed to obtain initial estimates. They were produced for the intercepts α_μ , and a single nonlinear effect $s_\mu(\cdot)$ formulated as a third order P-Spline of degree three with twelve knots. Hence, the following setting for the inflated beta distribution is considered:

$$\begin{aligned} \log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1 - \mu_i}\right) &= \alpha_\mu + s_\mu(\hat{H}_i), \\ \log\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{1 - \sigma_i}\right) &= \alpha_\sigma, \\ \log(v_i) &= \alpha_\nu, \\ \log(\tau_i) &= \alpha_\tau. \end{aligned}$$

This setting yielded an AIC score of -4,750, and most estimates are significantly different from zero except for those of α_τ (see Table 1). The nonlinear effects of the P-Spline are also significant. This model yielded a reasonable expectation for the absolute relative error (see Figure 3). A nonlinear trend produced a mean absolute relative error (MARE) based on the entropy values. Small values are produced for small entropy values, and as the entropy increases, higher MARE are produced to reflect more variability in the imputation process.

Table 1: Summary results for the first model.

<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t value</i>	<i>Pr(> t)</i>
α_μ	-2.19	0.04	-60.42	<2e-16 ***
$s_\mu(\hat{H}_i)$	4.98	0.21	23.92	<2e-16 ***
α_σ	-0.14	0.01	-9.81	<2e-16 ***
α_ν	-2.41	0.05	-50.07	<2e-16 ***
α_τ	-24.11	2965.82	-0.01	0.994

Figure 3: The scatterplot between entropy and absolute relative error and the fitted model predictions.

The second model accounts for additional effects based on the squared relative prediction differences D_i . The regression coefficients, β , were introduced along with their covariates in the following setting:

$$\begin{aligned} \log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1-\mu_i}\right) &= \alpha_\mu + \beta_{\mu,D}\hat{D}_i + s_\mu(\hat{H}_i), \\ \log\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{1-\sigma_i}\right) &= \alpha_\sigma + \beta_{\sigma,D}\hat{D}_i + \beta_{\sigma,H}\hat{H}_i, \\ \log(\nu_i) &= \alpha_\nu + \beta_{\nu,D}\hat{D}_i + \beta_{\nu,H}\hat{H}_i, \\ \log(\tau_i) &= \alpha_\tau. \end{aligned}$$

This new setting yielded an AIC score of -6,267 (a much lower value than the AIC computed for the first model). Therefore, this second model produced better results. In fact, most effects are significantly different from zero (see Table 2).

Table 2: Summary results for the second model.

<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t value</i>	<i>Pr(> t)</i>
α_μ	-2.43	0.04	-60.46	<2e-16 ***
$\beta_{\mu,D}$	2.51	0.11	23.24	<2e-16 ***
$s_\mu(\hat{H}_i)$	5.36	0.23	23.05	<2e-16 ***
α_σ	-0.58	0.04	-15.80	<2e-16 ***
$\beta_{\sigma,D}$	-1.03	0.15	-6.82	9.91e-12 ***
$\beta_{\sigma,H}$	2.55	0.23	11.23	<2e-16 ***
α_ν	-0.57	0.13	-4.44	9.24e-06 ***
$\beta_{\nu,D}$	-197.01	18.76	-10.50	<2e-16 ***
$\beta_{\nu,H}$	-7.45	1.14	-6.52	7.43e-11 ***
α_τ	-24.42	2965.88	-0.01	0.993

Larger values of squared prediction differences, \hat{D}_i , and median entropy, \hat{H}_i , are associated with high values of MARE. However, high values of \hat{D}_i substantially reduce the dispersion of the MARE, while high values of \hat{H}_i are found to have the opposite effect. Moreover, both \hat{D}_i and \hat{H}_i largely influence the probability of zero occurrences because both $\hat{\beta}_{\nu,D}$ and $\hat{\beta}_{\nu,H}$ are significant. In fact, when both covariates are set to zero, the probability of observing a zero outcome is approximately 0.4. However, when either \hat{D}_i or \hat{H}_i increases, the probability mass of the zeros, p_0 , rapidly decreases. This effect, in turn, increases the probability that an absolute relative error lies in the interval (0,1). In general, the few tracts in this dataset have absolute relative error equal to one. These data points are usually attributed to small tracts that do not provide enough information to model the probability mass of the outcomes one, i.e., p_1 .

The fitted values from the second model are used to calculate the SE for the imputed value \hat{A}_i as shown in (1). The final SE values are produced by rescaling the estimated uncertainty by the size of the tract. Tracts with higher levels of entropy or with large prediction differences are expected to have higher SEs. Therefore, these model-based SEs can be compared to the true error, which is defined to be $|\hat{A}_i - A_i|$.

It is important to note that the true errors are not normally distributed (see Figure 4). The points displayed below the green line represent true errors within one SE. Approximately 95% of the points are below the blue line, and they represent true errors within 1.96 SE. The points below the red line represent true errors within 3 SE (a standard threshold in statistical quality control; Montgomery and Woodall, 2008). About 99% of the true errors are below the red line. Thus, the imputed acreage is also accurate (i.e., close to the truth) because about 87% of the points are shown below the green line, which represents 1 SE. This imputation approach is more efficient when compared to a standard normal distribution where approximately 68% of the data would fall within $[-SE, SE]$.

Figure 4: The scatterplot between the model-based standard error (SE) on the x -axis and true error on the y -axis.

4. Conclusion

Using the GAMLSS to introduce more flexible functions to better capture nonlinearities in the data, a relationship between the summarized PCDL entropy and JAS imputation error for corn planted acres was found. However, the entropy information alone was not sufficiently informative to determine the variability of the JAS imputation errors. In fact, the squared relative difference between the predicted acreage summarized from the PCDL and the CSBs was included as a covariate to improve the model. This variable made probability for zero outcomes more precise and provided additional flexibility on the first two moments of the beta distribution.

The underlying relationships driving these results should be investigated by including more variables in the model. This study did not consider geographic effects on cropping patterns nor temporal dynamics that can affect the accuracy of both the PCDL and CSB predictions. Other characteristics of JAS, such as the farm size (expressed as acreage or income) and sampling information (such as the stratification) can be considered as well. Although the analysis in this paper only focuses on corn, it could be expanded to soybeans, winter wheat, or other commodities. The PCDL crop types that match specific targets in the JAS should be prioritized.

Influential tracts and outliers should be explored. Whether common attributes associated with the tracts having absolute relative error equal either to zero or one should be studied. Further tests should assess the model robustness due to the introduction of larger tracts. In fact, these tracts can be influential records that might improve the quantification of both variance and skewness.

A key finding from this paper is the potential to produce model-based SEs before current-year FSA data are available. This methodology should be carefully evaluated for providing the additional variability due to imputation when estimating the total error associated with crop estimates. This approach also has the potential of winnowing the tracts for which automatic imputation may produce unreliable results. However, to better understand what factors impact the out-of-sample reliability, future work should explore more states and cover a broader range of years. Finally, the algorithms behind the CSBs and PCDL are still evolving in an effort to produce more accurate predictions with related measures of uncertainty.

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